

A Comparative Study on YONO SBI Application and HDFC Net - Banking Application

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Abstract:

The rapid evolution of digital banking platforms has transformed the financial ecosystem in India, leading to widespread adoption of applications such as YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking. These platforms have redefined the way consumers interact with banks by offering seamless access to services like fund transfers, bill payments, investment options, and loan management. YONO SBI integrates lifestyle features with banking, enabling users to shop, book travel, and access financial products within a single application, while HDFC Net Banking emphasizes secure online transactions, account management, and personalized financial planning. With the increasing penetration of smartphones, internet connectivity, and government initiatives promoting digital banking, consumers today rely more on these platforms for routine financial activities, reducing dependence on physical branch visits. This study investigates the impact of YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking on consumer spending and saving behavior. It explores how instant and integrated banking options may encourage higher transaction frequency, diversified financial engagement, and reduced resistance to spending compared to traditional banking methods. The findings of this study will help understand the dual nature of digital banking tools, promoting convenience and efficiency while also influencing consumer tendencies toward both spending and structured savings.

Keywords: YONO SBI, HDFC Net Banking, Digital Banking Applications, Consumer spending, Saving Behavior, Digital Financial tools.

Introduction:

The emergence of digital banking platforms has reshaped the financial services industry in India, offering consumers faster, more accessible, and more efficient ways to manage their money. Among the leading applications, YONO SBI and HDFC NetBanking stand out as comprehensive tools that combine traditional banking functions with modern digital innovations. These platforms allow users to conduct a wide range of activities such as transferring funds, paying bills, monitoring investments, applying for loans, and accessing lifestyle services, thereby reducing the need for physical branch visits and cash-based transactions. With the rapid growth of smartphone usage, improved internet connectivity, and government initiatives encouraging digital financial

inclusion, consumers increasingly rely on these applications for everyday financial tasks. The convenience of instant transactions and one-click services has influenced spending behaviour, often encouraging frequent usage and lowering resistance compared to conventional banking methods. At the same time, features such as transaction histories, budgeting insights, and secure interfaces promote structured saving habits and financial discipline. This comparative study focuses on evaluating the impact of YONO SBI and HDFC NetBanking on consumer spending and saving behaviour. It aims to highlight the similarities and differences between the two platforms, examine the behavioural changes they trigger, and assess their

broader implications for personal financial management in the evolving digital economy.

Research Methodology:

Objective Of The Study:

1. To study the level of awareness and usage of YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking applications among consumers.
2. To examine the comparative impact of YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking on consumer saving and spending behavior.
3. To identify the benefits and challenges experienced by users while using YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking platforms.
4. To offer suggestions for improving consumer financial discipline through the effective use of YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking applications.

Hypothesis Of The Study:

H01: There is a significant relationship between age and satisfaction with YONO SBI/HDFC Net Banking.

H11: There is no significant relationship between age and satisfaction with YONO SBI/HDFC Net Banking.

H02: There is a significant difference between males and females in their preference for bill payment services.

H12: There is no significant difference between males and females in their preference for bill payment services.

Scope Of The Study:

This study focuses on understanding how digital banking applications, specifically YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking, influence the spending and saving behavior of consumers. It covers the benefits such as convenience, speed, integrated services, secure transactions, and financial tracking, as well as challenges like cybersecurity concerns, technical issues, and impulsive financial decisions. The study is limited to users of YONO SBI and HDFC Net Banking platforms and examines

behavioral changes, usage patterns, and consumer perceptions within a selected geographic area and time period.

Sampling:

- A. Area or Universe of research: Consumers in Navi Mumbai using YONO SBI and HDFC NetBanking for personal financial transactions.
- B. Sampling Method: Random sampling method
- C. Sample Size: 100 samples

Methods Of Data Collection:

Data collection is a systematic process of gathering observations or measurements. Under this study both the Sources of the data has been used i.e. Primary data and Secondary data.

Primary Data: Primary data was gathered through a questionnaire from consumers using YONO SBI and HDFC NetBanking.

Secondary Data: The sources of secondary data are collected from Internet, Books, Articles.

Data Analysis:

1. Data Analysis tools: For the purpose of analysis the information obtained through primary data the tools used are percentages, weighted average, etc.

2. Data Presentation tools: The tools used for presentation are: Tables, Graphs, Charts and Diagrams.

Literature Review:

A literature review is an overview of the previously published works on a topic. The term can refer to a full scholarly paper or a section of a scholarly work such as a book, or an article. A Few studies had been made which were indirectly helpful to this investigation. Reviews of such studies are presented below:

1. Singh (2020), His study on mobile banking apps in India highlighted that user interface, accessibility, and security are key drivers of satisfaction. He found HDFC NetBanking more streamlined, while SBI YONO was

valued for its integrated services beyond banking.

2. Kumar & Sinha (2020), They described SBI YONO as an integrated platform combining banking with e-commerce, offering services like insurance, shopping, and travel. Their findings emphasized its role as a one-stop solution for diverse financial needs.
3. Sharma (2021), He noted that YONO's integration of multiple services enhances convenience, making it attractive for users seeking both financial and lifestyle solutions in a single app.
4. Rao (2021), His research praised HDFC NetBanking for efficiency in core banking functions such as real-time transactions, bill payments, and loan management, positioning it as a reliable tool for focused banking.
5. Kaur (2019), She emphasized the importance of security and personalization, observing that HDFC's multi-layer authentication is considered more secure, while SBI YONO's biometric login is user-friendly but prone to occasional glitches.

Data Analysis And Interpretation:

Table No. 1: Gender based Analysis:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	55	55%
Female	45	45%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The gender-wise distribution of respondents shows that a majority are male, accounting for 55% of the total sample. Female respondents constitute 45%. This indicates that the survey sample is male-dominated, which may

influence certain findings based on gender-related perspectives.

Table No. 2: Age based Analysis:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
18-30	90	90%
31-45	6	6%
45-60	4	4%
61-Above	0	0%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The age-wise distribution shows that the majority of respondents (90%) fall within the 18–30 years category, making it the most dominant group in the study. This is followed by 6% of respondents in the 31–45 years group and 4% in the 45–60 years group, while no respondents were recorded in the 61 and above category. This pattern suggests that the survey primarily reflects the perceptions of younger consumers, with middle-aged and senior participants being comparatively fewer.

Table No. 3: Occupation based Analysis:

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Student	45	45%
Self Employed	38	38%
Business owner	9	9%
Homemaker	8	8%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The occupation-wise distribution indicates that students form the largest group (45%), reflecting strong participation from younger or academically engaged individuals. This is followed by self-employed respondents (38%), showing significant representation of independent earners. Business owners (9%) and homemakers (8%) make up smaller portions of the sample. Overall, the survey highlights that the majority of responses come from students and self-employed individuals, while business owners and homemakers are comparatively fewer.

Table No. 4: Bank-wise Distribution of Respondents

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
SBI	35	35%
HDFC	26	26%
OTHER	39	39%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The distribution shows that 39% of respondents use other banks, making it the largest category. SBI is chosen by 35%, while HDFC accounts for 26%. Overall, the data suggests that while SBI and HDFC together serve a significant portion of users, a considerable share of respondents rely on alternative banks to meet their banking needs.

Table No. 5: Frequency of Digital Banking Usage by Respondents

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Daily	57	57%
Weekly	19	19%
Monthly	9	9%
Rarely	15	15%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The data shows that 57% of respondents use digital banking services daily, making it the most common usage pattern. Weekly users account for 19%, while monthly users are 9% and 15% use services rarely. This indicates that digital banking has become a routine activity for the majority, with daily engagement dominating the trend.

Table No. 6: Features Most Commonly Used in Banking Applications

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Account management	13	13%
Transaction history	22	22%
Bill payments	33	33%
Fund transfers	18	18%
Other	14	14%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The data shows that bill payments are the most commonly used feature (33%), followed by transaction history (22%) and fund transfers (18%). Account management (13%) and other features (14%) are used less frequently. Overall, this indicates that respondents primarily rely on banking applications for routine financial activities like bill payments and transfers, while advanced or additional features see comparatively lower usage.

Table No. 7 Which banking app the respondents consider to be the most user-friendly ?

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
YONO SBI is better	19	19%
HDFC Net Banking is better	29	29%
Both are equally good	17	17%
Not sure	35	35%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The data shows that HDFC Net Banking is considered the most user-friendly by 29% of respondents, while YONO SBI is preferred by 19%. 17% feel both are equally user-friendly, and the largest share, 35%, remain unsure. This indicates that although HDFC leads in preference, a significant portion of users are undecided, reflecting mixed perceptions of banking app usability.

Table No. 8: Respondents’ Opinions on Better Bill Payment Services.

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
YONO SBI	19	19%
HDFC Net Banking	31	31%
Both are equal	22	22%
Not sure	28	28%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The analysis shows that the data shows 31% of respondents prefer HDFC Net Banking for bill payments, while 19% favor YONO SBI. 22% consider both equal and 28% are unsure, indicating mixed perceptions with HDFC holding a slight

Table No. 9: Respondents’ Ratings of Security Features – YONO SBI vs HDFC NetBanking

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
YONO SBI is more secure	18	19%
HDFC Net Banking is more secure	31	31%
Both are equally secure	27	27%
Not sure	24	24%
Total:	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The analysis shows that most respondents perceive HDFC Net Banking (31%) as more secure compared to YONO SBI (19%). A considerable proportion (27%) believe both platforms offer equal levels of security, while 24% remain uncertain about which app is safer. Overall, the findings suggest that HDFC Net Banking enjoys stronger trust among users, though a significant share acknowledges parity or expresses indecision, reflecting mixed perceptions of security in digital banking applications.

Raw Labels	18 - 30	31 - 45	45 - 60	Grand Total
Neutral	34	2	0	36
Somewhat dissatisfied	2	1	0	3
Somewhat satisfied	29	3	4	36
Very dissatisfied	1	0	0	1
Very satisfied	24	0	0	24
Grand Total	90	6	4	100

ANOVA Results Analysis:

ANOVA							
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	
Between Groups	450.67	2	225.33	3.09	0.0951	4.26	
Within Groups	656	9	72.89				
Total	1106.67	11					

Decision on Hypothesis:

The P-value (0.0951) > 0.05, which means we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between age and satisfaction levels with YONO SBI/HDFC Net Banking.

T – Test: The t-test is a statistical method used to compare the means of two groups and determine if the difference between them is statistically significant. It is commonly used when: (i) The

Hypothesis Testing:

Hypothesis testing is a statistical method used to make decisions or draw conclusions about a population based on data collected from a sample. It helps researchers test an assumption (called a hypothesis) by comparing it with actual evidence.

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance): ANOVA is a statistical method used to compare the means of three or more groups to determine if there is a significant difference between them. Instead of doing multiple t-tests, ANOVA allows us to test all groups in a single analysis.

1st Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant relationship between age and satisfaction with YONO SBI/HDFC Net Banking.

H0: There is no significant relationship between age and satisfaction with YONO SBI/HDFC Net Banking.

sample size is small. (ii) The population standard deviation is unknown.

2nd Hypothesis:

H1: There is a significant difference between males and females in their preference for bill payment services.

H0: There is no significant difference between males and females in their preference for bill payment services.

Raw Labels	Female	Male	Grand Total
Both are equal	15	7	22
HDFC Net Banking	11	20	31
Not sure	9	19	28
YONO SBI	10	9	19
Grand Total	45	55	100

t-Test Results Analysis:

	<i>Variable 1</i>	<i>Variable 2</i>
Mean Preference	18.75	25.75
Variance	306.92	404.92
Observations	4	4
Pearson Correlation	0.969	
Hypothesized Mean Diff	1	
Degrees of Freedom (df)	3	
t-Statistic	-2.99	
P(T<=t) One-Tail	0.0291	
t Critical One-Tail	2.3534	
P(T<=t) Two-Tail	0.0582	
t Critical Two-Tail	3.1824	

Decision on Hypothesis:

One-tailed test: Since P-value (0.0291) < 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0), meaning gender does influence bill payment service preference. Two-tailed test: Since P-value (0.0582) > 0.05, we fail to reject H_0 , meaning gender does not significantly influence bill payment service preference in a two-tailed.

Conclusion:

Summary of key findings:

- 1 Security Perceptions – 31% of respondents consider HDFC NetBanking more secure, while 19% favor YONO SBI; 27% rate both equally secure, and 24% remain unsure.
- 2 User-Friendliness – HDFC NetBanking is seen as more user-friendly (29%), compared to YONO SBI (19%), though 35% of respondents are undecided.
- 3 Bill Payment Services – HDFC NetBanking again leads (31%) in bill payment satisfaction, while 19% prefer YONO SBI, and 22% find both equal.

- 4 Loading Speed – Respondents generally rate HDFC NetBanking faster in loading speed compared to YONO SBI, though many users find them comparable.
- 5 Feature Usage – Bill payments (33%) and transaction history (22%) are the most commonly used features, showing reliance on apps for routine financial activities

Conclusion:

The comparative analysis of SBI YONO and HDFC NetBanking highlights clear consumer preferences and usage trends. HDFC NetBanking consistently emerges as the stronger platform, rated higher in security, user-friendliness, bill payment services, and speed. In contrast, YONO SBI lags behind in these areas, though it remains relevant for a portion of users who value its accessibility and integration with SBI's broader services.

The findings also reveal that routine financial activities such as bill payments and fund transfers dominate app usage, while advanced features see lower engagement. Despite differences between the two apps, overall perceptions of digital payment platforms remain positive, with most

respondents recognizing their role in enhancing convenience, reducing reliance on cash, and supporting better financial management.

To remain competitive, both apps must continue to focus on security, speed, and customer-centric improvements, while also addressing challenges such as transaction failures and privacy concerns. Building trust, improving user experience, and expanding awareness will be essential for sustaining growth in India's rapidly evolving digital banking landscape

References:

Bibliography:

1. Balakrishnan, L. (2016). Factors Affecting Mobile Banking Services – An Empirical Study. ISBR Management Journal Research Center, 1(2), 23–29.
2. Bamoriya, P. (2012). Mobile Banking in India: Barriers in Adoption and Service Preference. Internal Review – A Journal of Management, 5(1), 1–7.
3. Bhatt, S. (2020). An Empirical Study of Factors Affecting Adoption of M-Commerce

in India. Journal of Marketing Advances and Practices, 3(1), 42–60.

4. Ghodke, S., & Amit, P. W. (2013). To Study Consumer Awareness & Perception Towards Usage of Mobile Banking. IBMRD's Journal of Management and Research, 2(2), 80–86.
5. Husis-Fen-Lin. (2011). An Empirical Investigation of Mobile Banking Adoption: The Effect of Innovation Attributes and Knowledge-Based Trust. International Journal of Information Management, 31(3), 252–260.

Webliography:

- <https://www.onlinesbi.sbi>
- <https://www.hdfcbank.com>
- <https://www.jetir.org/JETIR2504851.pdf>
- <https://www.ijfmr.com/papers/2024/5/27971.pdf>
- <https://www.bajajfinserv.in/hdfc-bank-vs-sbi-bank>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/State_Bank_of_India
- <https://www.hdfcbank.com/personal/ways-to-bank/mobilebanking/hdfc-bank-mobilebanking-app>